

An Attempt to Improve the Efficiency of Chat Bots by Providing Multilingual Support

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Abstract - Chatbots are conversational agents that use a computer programme to have intelligent conversations with users. These are virtual people who can use interactive textual skills to communicate with any human being. These are applications that make use of AI and Machine Learning Platform. NLP is widely used in the training of chatbots. Chatbots were created to see if machines could fool users into thinking they were conversing with humans rather than robots. As this concept gained traction, numerous companies began developing chatterbots for a variety of purposes. There are numerous platforms on which to build a chatbot; however, this paper focuses on developing a customer support chatbot that supports multi-language communication using the Python programming language. To clear up basic doubts, we can communicate with the chatbot in any language. To predict the properties of the new data, the chatbot is trained using a data set. It first receives the user query, then analyses it before returning the response. Chatbots can be linked to web browsers on various operating systems and can be used as an Android application as well.

Keywords – Multilingual Chatbot, Natural Language Processing (NLP), Machine Learning.

I. INTRODUCTION

In chat-bots, a computer software is used to facilitate conversations with humans. With users, have intelligent dialogue. They are digital a person who can converse with any human being interactivity in text. These are applications that run on Platform for machine learning and artificial intelligence (AI). NLP is crucial for the chatbot's training. The idea of chatbots was developed to determine whether the Users could be duped by robots into believing that they are genuinely conversing with humans, not machines. As the idea develops Popularly, numerous businesses began creating Chatbots for

various purposes. Numerous platforms are available for construct the chatbot, but here we mostly focus on python-based chatbot development.

II. PROPOSED SYSTEM

We are so familiar with chatbots through various websites and social media platforms, but most of the chatbots are available in English language and majority of the chatbots does not support other languages especially regional languages. So, it is very relevant to have chatbots with multilingual communication capability. Through this system, a user can communicate with a chatbot in multiple languages as well as users from various region can chat with the bot with their own language.

III. REQUIREMENTS

Editor - PyCharm Community Edition or Visual Studio Code; *Framework* – Flask; *Libraries* – NLTK, Pickle, NumPy, Googletrans, TensorFlow, Keras.

WORKING OF CHATBOT

Step-by-Step

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

The chatbot is implemented in Flask framework with the help of PyCharm Community Edition as the editor in python language. Let us see the implementation step-by-step:

1. Create a Virtual Environment

```
C:\Windows\System32\cmd.exe
Microsoft Windows [Version 10.0.19044.2130]
(c) Microsoft Corporation. All rights reserved.

C:\Users\Albin Thomas Joseph\OneDrive\Desktop\Chatbot-app>py -m venv env
```

2. Install Required Modules

```
1. pip install tensorflow
2. pip install keras
3. pip install pickle
4. pip install nltk
5. pip install flask
```

3. Setup Requisites for Flask Framework

4. Create Dataset in Json file

```
{
  "intents": [
    {
      "tag": "greeting",
      "patterns": ["Hi", "How are you", "Is anyone there?", "Hello", "Good day"],
      "responses": ["Hello, how can I help you?", "Ask me for any help!", "Hi there"],
      "context_set": ""
    },
    {
      "tag": "goodbye",
      "patterns": ["Bye", "See you later", "Goodbye"],
      "responses": ["See you later, thanks for visiting", "Have a nice day", "Bye!"]
    },
    {
      "tag": "thanks",
      "patterns": ["Thanks", "Thank you", "That's helpful"],
      "responses": ["Happy to help!", "Any time!", "My pleasure"]
    }
  ]
}
```

5. Prepare the data (preprocessing)

When working with text data, several preprocessing steps must be completed before we can build a machine learning or deep learning model. We must use a variety of operations to preprocess the data based on the requirements. Tokenization is the most simple and straightforward process you can do with text data. The process of breaking down a large text into smaller pieces, such as words, is known as tokenization. We work our way through the patterns, tokenizing the sentence with the nltk.word tokenize() function and appending each word in the words list.

In addition, we create a tag class list.

```
for intent in intents['intents']:
    for pattern in intent['patterns']:

        #tokenize each word
        w = nltk.word_tokenize(pattern)
        words.extend(w)
        #add documents in the corpus
        documents.append((w, intent['tag']))

    # add to our classes list
    if intent['tag'] not in classes:
        classes.append(intent['tag'])

# lemmatize and lower each word and remove duplicates
words = [lemmatizer.lemmatize(w.lower()) for w in words if w not in ignore_words]
words = sorted(list(set(words)))
# sort classes
classes = sorted(list(set(classes)))
# documents = combination between patterns and intents
print(len(documents), "documents", documents)
# classes = intents
print(len(classes), "classes", classes)
# words = all words, vocabulary
print(len(words), "unique lemmatized words", words)

pickle.dump(words, open('texts.pkl', 'wb'))
pickle.dump(classes, open('labels.pkl', 'wb'))
```

6. Create training data

Now we will create the training data, which will include both the input and output. Our pattern will be our input, and our output will be the class to which our pattern belongs. However, because the computer does not understand text, we will convert it to numbers.

7. Create the model

We now have enough training data to build a three-layer deep neural network. We use the Keras sequential API for this. After training our model for 200 epochs, we achieved 100% accuracy. This model will be referred to as 'model.h5.'

8. Predict the response

Create a new file called 'app.py' to predict sentences and receive user feedback. We'll load the trained model and then use a graphical user interface to predict the bot's response. We'll write some functions to identify the class and then retrieve a random response from the list of responses because the model will only tell us which class it belongs to. We load the pickle files 'texts.pkl' and 'labels.pkl' that we created when we trained our model and import the necessary packages. We must use the same input as we did during training to predict the class. As a result, we'll write some functions to perform text preprocessing, and then we'll get a random response from the list of intents based on the class's prediction. We will now create a graphical user interface with

HTML, CSS, and the Flask framework. We will take the user's input message and retrieve and display the bot's response on the GUI using the helper functions we wrote. The response message will be written in the same language as the query. Now, start the chatbot.

To run the chatbot, two files are required: training.py and app.py. First, we train the model with the following terminal command:

```
C:\Windows\System32\cmd.exe
Microsoft Windows [Version 10.0.19044.2130]
(c) Microsoft Corporation. All rights reserved.
C:\Users\Albin Thomas Joseph\OneDrive\Desktop\Chatbot-app>python training.py

C:\Users\Albin Thomas Joseph\OneDrive\Desktop\Chatbot-app>python app.py
```

V. IMPLEMENTATION OF MULTILINGUAL FACILITY

We are adding multilingual capability to the chatbot with the help of the Googletrans library. Googletrans is a Python library that uses the Google Translate API and is completely free. This employs the Google Translate Ajax API to invoke methods such as detect and translate.

```
from googletrans import Translator
```

```
translator = Translator()

def chatbot_response(msg):
    op = translator.detect(msg)
    if op.lang == 'en':
        ints = predict_class(msg, model)
        res = getResponse(ints, intents)
    else:
        language = op.lang
        op2 = translator.translate(msg, dest="en")
        ints = predict_class(op2.text, model)
        resp = getResponse(ints, intents)
        resp2 = translator.translate(resp, dest=language)
        res = resp2.text

    return res
```

We use language 'detect' function and language 'translate' function from *googletrans* library to make bot to respond in multiple languages. The language detect function will detect the language of user query and with the help of that, we can

translate the query into English by using language translator function and hence retrieve the bot response according to the translated query. After successfully retrieving the response, we are translating the response back to the language that we detected initially and this is how it works with all languages.

VI. OUTCOME OF THE IMPLEMENTATION

VII. CONCLUSION

The project's goal is to reduce human workload and provide faster responses to user queries in any language. Users used to send a query email to the site administrator, and the site administrator would respond to all such emails, including ours, within a few days. Chatbots can overcome this delay by responding to the user's request or query immediately. To respond to user requests more quickly, many websites, including those of banks, educational institutions, and businesses, have created chatbots. Chatbots are artificial machines that mimic human behaviour. This paper describes the multilingual chatbot's overall development and operation.

VIII. FUTURE SCOPE

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